

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Analysis%			μ_{eff} B.M. 300°K
		Metal	Nitrogen	Anion	
Co(LH) ₂ Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Pink	11.52 (11.69)	16.80 (16.67)	13.95 (14.07)	5.00
Co(LH) ₂ Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Flesh Coloured	9.86 (9.94)	14.05 (14.17)	26.62 (26.96)	4.80
Co(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Pinkish White	10.48 (10.58)	19.97 (20.10)	—	4.77
Co(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Pinkish White	11.05 (11.14)	15.69 (15.88)	18.20 (18.14)	4.83
Ni(LH) ₂ Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	11.58 (11.65)	16.75 (16.67)	13.95 (14.07)	4.00
Ni(LH) ₂ Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	9.78 (9.90)	13.99 (14.17)	26.78 (26.97)	3.01
Ni(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	10.48 (10.54)	20.00 (20.11)	—	2.93
Ni(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Sky blue	10.98 (11.10)	15.95 (15.88)	18.05 (18.15)	2.91
Cu(LH)Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	17.60 (17.75)	11.58 (11.75)	19.61 (19.84)	1.37
Cu(LH)Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Dirty Green	14.07 (14.21)	9.52 (9.41)	35.53 (35.81)	1.48
Cu(LH)(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light blue	15.33 (15.45)	17.18 (17.05)	—	1.44
Cu(LH)SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Greenish blue	16.48 (16.59)	10.78 (10.93)	24.87 (25.10)	1.43
Cu(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	11.20 (11.30)	19.84 (19.94)	—	1.80
Cu(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	11.77 (11.89)	15.58 (15.74)	16.78 (17.03)	1.83

* Figures in the parenthesis represent the calculated values.

suffers a depression of 20-55 cm⁻¹ in the chelated species indicating the participation of the carbonyl group in bonding to the metal ion through its oxygen atom. As is observed here, bonding from the carbonyl oxygen and the terminal -NH₂ of the acid hydrazides is a well established fact^{1,2}.

In view of the subnormal magnetic moment values of the 1 : 1 Cu(II) complexes, the following dimeric formulation (Fig. 1), in which the carbonyl group act as a bridge between two Cu(II) centres, is proposed :

Fig. 1.

Cryomagnetic studies on the 1 : 1 Cu(II) complexes are being done and will be reported soon.

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A Study of Vanadyl(IV) Complex of Fluorescein—Thermal Studies of Amine Adducts. Part-VII.

LEELA PARDESHI and R. A. BHOBE*

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India

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DETAILED studies on complexes of fluorescein including that of vanadyl⁵, have already been reported¹⁻⁵. The vanadyl ion having a strong and dominant axial field and four ligand moieties

* Senior author to whom all correspondence should be addressed.

NOTES

flat in the equatorial plane can accommodate⁵, trans to vanadyl oxygen, the solvent molecules of NH_3 , $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ and $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ to give an octahedral complex/adduct. Thermal dissociation of such ammonia and ammine adducts of vanadylfluorescein complex give ΔH , ΔF and ΔS values (K cal/mole/degree) as 11.85, 3.24, 28.90 for NH_3 adduct, 14.70, 2.89, 39.60 for CH_3NH_2 adduct, 15.68, 3.19, 41.75 for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ adduct and 21.40, 3.20, 54.50 for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ adduct.

The vanadyl complex of fluorescein is a violet black paramagnetic entity whose structure has been reported by us⁵. It was interesting to observe that this complex formed adducts with NH_3 (dark violet), with CH_3NH_2 (brownish violet), with $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ (dirty brown) and with $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ (dark brownish black). Pressure studies indicated that thermal dissociation of these adducts are smooth and measurable.

Preparation and Analysis :

The liquid amines formed adducts with $\text{VO}(\text{FLCN})_4$ easily when the latter was suspended in ethanol and when a slight stoichiometric excess amine was mixed at $\sim 30^\circ$. The NH_3 adduct was formed when gaseous NH_3 was passed for twenty-four hours through finely powdered $\text{VO}(\text{FLCN})_4$. In all the cases, the adducts formed were flushed thoroughly with pure nitrogen gas. The analysis was carried out with the usual microtechniques and are given in Table 1 (V = Vanadium metal).

TABLE 1

Adduct of	%elements (obsd)				%elements (calcd)			
	V	C	H	N	V	C	H	N
Ammonia	4.11	68.03	3.44	—	3.86	68.19	3.34	—
Methyl amine	3.66	68.98	3.39	45.06	3.58	68.30	3.45	45.16
Ethyl amine	3.51	68.46	3.59	30.96	3.56	68.40	3.56	31.11
Butyl amine	3.40	68.79	3.82	15.94	3.48	68.74	3.76	16.09

Experimental

The adducts were carefully heated with an automatic thermoregulator. Pressures generated were transmitted to Hg in capillary and the heights recorded with the help of a cathetometer, recording 0.001 cm accurately. The results were reproducible with fresh samples of the adduct, and also reversible which is the prerequisite for thermodynamic calculations given below.

Results and Discussion

The values of T (°K) vs pressures (mm) are not given in tabular form but are depicted as plots of $10^3/T$ vs log P in Fig. 1 and the slopes and ΔH (K cal) values are set out in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF SLOPES FROM THE PLOTS OF log P vs $10^3/T$ AND ΔH VALUES

Adduct with :	Slope $\times 10^{-2}$	ΔH (K cal/mole)
Ammonia	5.99	11.85
Methyl amine	7.50	14.70
Ethyl amine	7.92	15.68
Butyl amine	10.75	21.40

The free energy data ΔF and the entropies ΔS (at 25°) were calculated by standard Eyring equations. The relevant values are shown below (Table 3).

TABLE 3— ΔF AND ΔS ALONG WITH ΔH VALUES (TABLE 2) FOR THE AMMONIA AND AMINE ADDUCTS OF $\text{VO}(\text{FLCN})_4$

Thermodynamic quantities (K cal/mole)	Ammonia adduct	CH_3NH_2 adduct	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ adduct	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ adduct
ΔH	11.85	14.70	15.68	21.40
ΔF	3.24	2.89	3.19	3.20
ΔS	28.92	39.60	41.75	54.50

A similar work on gaseous boron trimethyl adducts with NH_3 and amines⁶ give comparable results in that ΔH values for this adduct range from 3.75 to 23.48 K cal/mole and ΔS from 39.90 for the ammonia adduct to 44.70 for the butyl adduct, in both the cases, showing an increasing trend as the number of carbon atoms increase. A slight deviation in the case of ammonia adduct may be attributed to changes in the rotational entropy losses of the ligand when NH_3 molecule gets co-ordinated within the crystal lattice in the present case as against the gaseous molecules of boron trimethyl ammonia adduct⁷.

$$(\Delta S \text{ VO}(\text{FLCN})_4 \cdot \text{NH}_3 = 28.92 ; \Delta S (\text{CH}_3)_3\text{B} \cdot \text{NH}_3 = 39.90).$$

Since log P vs $1/T$ plots (Figs. 1 to 4) are fairly on a straight line, it may be assumed that enthalpy changes are almost constant and ΔS varies inversely with temperature. That means, at the expense of heat absorbed, the vapour pressure of the ligand (FLCN) gets raised. Table 4 below gives an idea of net changes that take place between temperatures 25° to 60° .

TABLE 4—NET CHANGES (cals/mole) IN THE AMINE ADDUCTS OF $\text{VO}(\text{FLCN})_4$

Amine adduct	NH_3	CH_3NH_2	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$
ΔS at 25°C	28.90	39.60	41.75	54.50
ΔS at 60°C	29.10	34.40	42.05	59.60
Net changes	-0.20	1.20	-2.30	-5.10

C_v value for NH_3 is taken as 6.57 cal/mole/degree⁸. It seems that for 35° change (25° to 60°), the changes in vapour pressure of the NH_3 adduct correspond to change of entropy effect -0.20, which

may be ascribed to transfer of NH_3 or amine molecule from the solid to the gaseous state. The translational entropies ΔS (trans) can be easily calculated⁹ and the absolute values ΔS (abs) by standard equations¹⁰.

These are listed in Table 5.

Adduct	ΔS (trans)	ΔS (abs)	ΔS (ob.d)
NH_3	34.53	45.50	28.90
CH_3NH_2	36.34	57.96	39.60
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	37.70	69.06	41.75
$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$	39.20	84.42	54.50

The values in Table 5 clearly indicates that heavier the amine, greater is the contribution to

translational entropy. May be, factors such as hydrogen bonding are playing a dominant role in the distribution of entropies.

In the Table 6, competitive factor between NH_3 and other amines has been brought out. It gives one a rough idea about the relative structural effects when a ligand A_1 replaces A_2 as

It will be observed from the data (Table 6) that when ammonia as a ligand is replaced by $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ or when CH_3NH_2 by $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$, the entropy changes are exceptionally large thus indicating that the size of the replacing ligand plays a vital role.

TABLE 6—COMPETITIVE FACTORS INVOLVED IN REPLACEMENT OF LIGAND A₂ BY A₁

A ₂	A ₁	ΔF _{2,000} cals/mole	ΔH _{2,000} cals/mole	ΔS _{2,000} cals/mole/degree
NH ₃	CH ₃ NH ₂	+350	-2850	-10.70
NH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	+300	-3850	-12.85
NH ₃	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	+40	-9550	-25.60
CH ₃ NH ₂	C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	-300	-980	-2.00
CH ₃ NH ₂	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	-210	-6700	-14.90
C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	-10	-5700	+12.75

VO₂²⁺ will have a square pyramidal configuration. It is expected that this will assume either a regular or distorted octahedron structure when the ammonia or amine molecules are added to it. Search of literature¹¹⁻¹³ reveals a distorted octahedron structure for a vanadyl ion. With ammonia adduct, free energy changes seem to be maximum and decreases somewhat when the length of carbon chain in the amine added increases. The entropy effects are in reverse order. The order of the entropy units for butyl amine adduct predicts that a spontaneous replacement in this case is rather difficult. There are approximations involved in assuming a regular octahedron structure for VO₂²⁺ complex. In fact, crystal field theory predicts that the change from a regular octahedron to the square pyramidal structure is associated with an increased stability. The data presented in Table 6 merely shows that variations in symmetry of the complex molecule may take place and a preferred configuration will be assumed by the complex molecule when the ligand A gets attached to it loosely.

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Extraction and Complexometric Determination of Copper in Brass using Dimethyl Glyoxime as an Indicator

MONOJIT BAKSHI GUPTA

Central Laboratory, Indian Standards Institution,
New Delhi-110 002, (India)

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DIMETHYL Glyoxime¹ has already been used as an indicator for the complexometric titration of copper by the present author. The use of dimethyl glyoxime in analytical chemistry is well known. It has been used for the determination² of Ni, Pd(II), Pt(II), Iron(II) and Bismuth.

This paper reports the use of dimethyl glyoxime as an indicator for the complexometric titration of copper in brass or bronze samples.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

- (i) EDTA solution : a stock solution of 0.1M EDTA was prepared by dissolving 37.23 gm of EDTA (Sodium salt) in 1 litre of distilled water.
- (ii) Dimethyl Glyoxime (2%) : Prepared by dissolving in absolute alcohol.
- (iii) EDTA solution (4%) : Prepared in distilled water.
- (iv) Sodium diethyl dithio carbamates (1%) : The solution is prepared in distilled water.
- (v) Ammonium Hydroxide : Dilute (2%)
- (vi) Tartaric Acid : Solid
- (vii) Ethyl acetate : B.D.H/E. MERCK
- (viii) Silver nitrate solution : 2% in distilled water.

Procedure : 0.5 gm drillings of the brass or bronze sample is dissolved in dilute nitric acid (1 : 2) and tartaric acid (about 0.2 gm) in a beaker and transferred in a 250 ml volumetric flask and the solution is diluted upto the mark. 250 ml of the solution is drawn in a separating funnel. 15 ml of EDTA solution (4%) is added to it, the pH is maintained at 8.5 with ammonium hydroxide. Now